

A STUDY ON ORGANIZATIONAL BEHAVIOUR IN KIDS SCHOOL

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Abstract: The aim of this article is to explore the organizational behavior through the lenses of human relation theory and attributive theory of an institute by analyzing four themes that include people, structure, technology and external environment. This study suggests the methodology of considering the inward and outer elements that influence the performance of a person which directly impacts on efficiency of an institution. The examination highlights on human factors being the center of any association and the significance of giving such approval by making representative benevolent condition, joining valuable resources and helpful policy. Key target of this investigation is making an educational organization aware of capitalizing by their human resources and finding that equalization to get trust from the employees and enlarge their productivity. Key findings of this investigation are to obtain the current status of organizational behavior of teaching and non-teaching staff of private kids School, Far Western, Nepal and expected behavior from the human resources, a foundation must put their time in behavioral modification and keep on actualizing it.

Keywords: *organizational behavior, people, structure, technology and external environment*

I. INTRODUCTION

The success of any institutional organizations depends upon the effectiveness and ability of the management and the effectiveness of the management depends upon the human expertise and needs and targets of individuals. Organizational behavior refers to the behavior of the individuals within the organizations, the reason being, organizations can operate efficiently, if the human resources are skilled and capable. Organizational behavior is a study related to people working individually or in a team. It relates to expected behavior from individuals who work for an organization and how certain components bring variation in productivity for each individual. Study of human behavior is important because it is the human factor that contributes to productivity. According to Kondalkar (2007), organizational behavior is a field of study that investigates the impact that individuals, groups and organizational structure have on behavior within the organization, for the purpose of applying such knowledge towards improving an organizational effectiveness. Robbins (2012) defines organizational behavior as a systematic study of the actions and attitudes that people exhibit within organizations. Padhaya P. R and friends (2021), due to the lack of the ethics and morality in the authority of the academic organization, limitations of time and lack of proper adequate knowledge about the proper use of performance appraisal, authority is not practicing it effectively.

The purpose of this study was to explore the current status of staff of school through a narrative inquiry on organizational behavior and practices in rendering their services. There are four main components which are directly linked with the organization's functionality and output: people, structure, technology and external environment. This case study focuses on these components in correlation with the Human Relations Theory by (Elton Mayo and Fritz Jules Roethlisberger, 1930), which covers the importance of people for productivity and Attributive Theory which covers the cause and effect of structure, technology and external environment.

II. METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH OF THE STUDY

We conducted a qualitative narrative inquiry by the key informant interviews with people who knew what was going on in the research scope. The in-depth key informants' interviews were conducted to gain an understanding of the perspectives, behavior and generate recommendations for the main purpose of the research. Data were analyzed and interpreted under Human Relation Theory and Attributive Theory.

III. FINDINGS

THEME 1: PEOPLE AS A VALUE SYSTEM FOR IMPROVEMENT OF ORGANIZATION

(P1) said that her school focuses on quality rather than quantity. She said that we solve problem by sharing with ma'am (principal) and find the solution. She was satisfied with relation with her coworkers including teaching and non-teaching staffs. (P2) said that school works on core development of children and she was satisfied while sharing it. She said that only few people understand what school does for children. She showed dissatisfaction that school has not primary level and have to send children for grade one in another school. She said that she solves problem with own at first then she directly goes to principal and seek help. She was satisfied that school recognizes her strength and encourage further. She has not any problem regarding with relation issues among her coworkers including teaching and non-teaching. She sits with her coworkers if any problem arises. (P3) said her school management part is strong. But she showed her dissatisfaction in term of advertisement and marketing. She involved in open discussion with management in problem. She brings possible solutions and solve with her team. She is well engaging in sharing her ideas and implementing it as well. She discusses openly if any problem comes. Her management encourages bringing solution of problem and solving it together. (P4) only knew about school was that the school is for small children. She said that if number of students increased it would be good for her and as well as others. She takes suggestion with friends if problem comes in her work. She has not face any type of discrimination from teaching staffs and other people in the organization.

When we asked our participants whether they felt valued within their organization and their working environment suitable, one of the participants stated

"In my view, I feel appreciated and motivated by our supervisors as we are given an open space to express our views. The relationship we share is cordial with all staff members and the working environment is the strongest element of the school."

From the data given by the participant, it implies that the employees are given value for their contribution and they are acknowledged. The staff of the school is given utmost priority by their institute and they are happy with the work place.

If we merge the Dale Carnegie theory on 'How to Win Friends and Influence People' and 'Need Hierarchy Theory' by Abraham Maslow, we came to the understanding that for achieving success at a workplace, an institute needs satisfied employees. They seek for cooperation, appreciation and suitable working environment which lead to higher performance from both individual and organization.

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We found that our participants enjoyed the environment created and maintained at the school. There was an open and healthy space in the institute and their opinions were validated. Apart from few monetary issues, the staff was happy to receive emotional and professional supports from the school.

THEME 2: INDUCTION, INFORMATION AND STRUCTURAL NEED OF THE SCHOOL.

(P1) said that she was not aware with policy manual of the school. She knows few things about the leave policy but she is not sure with all. She did not know that exact statement for the vision and mission of the school. She got very clear information when something happened in school. She feels quite involved in decision making in different activities of school. She finds the need for gatekeeper as feel finds it difficult to open gate in the morning. It would have been better if there were somebody to open the gate and take care of school compound when there were no teachers. (P2) also has the same experience with the policy of the school and vision statement. She says that she had been provided with job description but she was not inducted with employee's policy manual and vision statement. She thinks that school has motives for holistic development of the student so she incorporates the motives with lesson plan she makes for the daily activities. She further states that they have regular face to face staff meeting with school principal where principal listens to them and involves staff members in decision making. She also mentioned the need of gatekeeper in school as there are no one take of the visitor and security. (P3) says that she is somehow aware to the policy that school has for their employee. She said that she knows about the provision in policy on how the SMC has to deal with the staff member. She also stated that the policy has space for the development of the individuals. She said that she is confused with the vision statement of the school. She can't exactly remember for the vision statement. She is very well engaged in decision making of the school activities as she is included in all the staff meetings. She doesn't see any need for the structural improvement. She is acquainted with the manpower available in school. (P4) says that she is not aware with the policy of the school. She doesn't know about the facilities provided by school and her specific job roles. She is instructed for job she has to do and she is not satisfied with what she is doing. She is not aware with the vision statement and work procedures. She also doesn't see any structural change and need for now. She is quite satisfied with what is provided and available.

Structural design of the institute plays good role in development of the school, satisfaction of the employee and legally strong institute. When we hire a new working staff for any organization, if we induce and orient the staff well in the beginning, the performance of the staff will be very high as the expectations are made clear. The induction of the employee with policy and vision statement makes the clear expectations and working environment remains safe and understanding because both parties know what to do and how. Involving employees in decision making boosts their confidence and they have the sense of belongingness. This has a positive impact on individual performance. It is good for individual staff member to see the structural need of the institute as they can feel the need and necessity in the field.

THEME 3: TECHNOLOGY AS A BANE AND A BOON.

We asked our first participant, (Participant 1), on how she experienced technology in her teaching role. She replied that basic technological tool is applied within her school as per necessity. In this line, we again asked her that how technology has impact on your teaching role. She narrated:

"Yes, we do use mobile, computer, TV, internet and various technological tools as per necessity. These are compulsory things in modern world. Frequently, we share our issues by face-to-face approach. However, when we are not in school, we use mobile phone to communicate. Somehow, its misuse by students created problems. Some children were complained for mobile and TV addiction."

After going through her experiences on use of technology, we came to know that she faced the boons and the banes. As we probed into her experiences, we understood her role as teacher, she has experiences and stories of using modern technological tools such as mobile phone, computer, television, and internet. We found her strong claim on proper use of technology to communicate with each other, which is compulsory things in the modern world. With the support of her experiences, we understood that technology has dark side also. She explores that several students got difficulties by over use of mobile, television or such gadgets. This exposes that technology has good and bad both side, which helps to enhance organizational behavior of teachers, however its uncontrolled use can ruin the remains.

We also queried the second participant, (**Participant 2**), on how she practiced technology in her teaching. She responded that technology is used as the essential things for 21st century development tool within her school role. In this line, we again asked her that how technology has impact on your teaching role. She narrated:

"We use mobile, computer, TV, sound system and so on. We use TV to show educational and entertainment material as per children's need. Technology is essential things for the 21st century development, so we used it as schedule for students. However, there are several problems of technology such as overuse and/or misused of mobile, gadgets, TV etc. by students. We give consultation to the parents for boundaries. We use technology for communicating with other."

Her experiences explore the use of technology as edutainment and communication tool. She used mobile, computer, television, and sound system for communication and teaching purpose. We came to know that she also experienced the several cases of overusing or misusing of the gadgets by students. However, it essential things for 21st century for students growth and development. As we probed into her experiences, we understood her role as teacher, she experienced the boons and banes of technology in her career.

Later, we questioned the third participant, (**Participant 3**), on how she practiced technology in her teaching profession. She answered that technology is used as the essential things for 21st century development tool within her school role. In this line, we again asked her that how technology has impact on your teaching role. She narrated:

"We do use technological product such as TV once or twice in a week. These shows are based on theme. We use group chat on Facebook messenger, generally talks are focused on school and children. As more, we share related materials on it. Technologies help to learn fast. We also use internet to learn more and advance things on internet. However, there are several dark sides of technology. Many kids talk about cartoon characters."

Her experiences explore that the television is used as the technological tool. It is routine and theme based. She also used internet services such as messenger and google for teaching and communication purpose. We came to know that she also shares the profession related materials on her messenger group chat as another member do. As we probed into her practices, we understood that she experienced technology help to learn fast, however sometimes kids follow the acting cartoon characters. It is just like as boons and banes in her career.

At last, we asked our fourth participant, (**Participant 4**), on how technology is practiced in her profession. She answered that technology is not used as the regular tool within her school profession. In this line, we again asked her that how technology has impact on your non-teaching role. She narrated:

"Technology is good for learning but it bothers the parents by overuse or misuse like as me. Several children including mine watch television till midnights or use mobile phones to play. For such situations, we work as bridge between school, parents and students. School management uses phone call to provide some notice."

Her experiences explore that the television and mobile distract the learning environment of children. Several children overuse these gadgets till midnights. In this situation, we explored that she tries to the fill the gap between school, parents and students. However, we came to know that she also believes the technology is good for learning. She uses mobile phone to communicate.

THEME 4: COPING THE ENVIRONMENT BY THE USE OF NATURAL AND CULTURAL THEME

When we asked our first participant, (Participant 1), how she explain the natural and cultural environment as external factors to the school in some words, she stated that natural environment as trees, plantation as more as disasters, bad weather and cultural environment as tradition and modernization. In this line, we further investigated that how she copes the nature and culture as her teaching profession. She narrated:

"We connect our kids with the nature to love it and nurture it. For instance, we are preparing for world environment day. Whole school will celebrate this event as a main theme. We also teach our students take precautions from disasters; bad weather as more make able to cope with changes. We use "Namaste", "Good morning/afternoon" and "Shubha prabhat" all to our students routinely so that, they can learn modern trends of greetings as well as our traditional greetings. We also create several concepts and implement with the consent of management after proper group planning."

After going through her practices on various programs such as world environment day or any occasion, they create several concepts, plan in group, take permission from management and implement properly. She asserted that her school is implementing both tradition and modernization. For instance, use of Namaste, Shubha Prabhat as traditional greeting, as same as "Good morning/afternoon" as modern trends of greeting. She explores that she taught her students to take precautions from natural disasters as more as make able to cope the environmental changes.

We also queried the second participant, (Participant 2), on how she explained the natural and cultural environment as external factors to the school in some words, she stated that natural environment as plantation, conservation, disaster and cultural environment as various programs fashion. In this line, we again asked her how she cope the nature and culture as her teaching profession. She narrated:

"We create sense about plantation, nature conservation and various things to connect students with nature. We have frequent outdoor programs. We teach student about safety measure from disasters such as earthquake, flood etc. We take precautions for such disasters. We conduct various programs such as cultural dress-show using ramps. We provide notice to the students and parents on these programs. If we felt any necessary programs to the students' development, we search and provide them. Our suggestions are accepted and implemented as per necessity within organization."

Her statement explores that she and her fellows create sense about plantation, natural conservation as more as connect students with nature. They also teach the safety measure against the disasters such as earthquake and flood. Further, she added that they also take precautions. As we probed into her experiences, we understood her role as teacher, she conducted various programs such

as cultural dress-show and involve the parents. We came to know that she also searched the necessary programs for students and implement after approval.

Afterward, we questioned the third participant, (Participant 3), on how she explained the natural and cultural environment as external factors to the school in some words. She answered that seasonal changes and disasters are related words to the natural environment whereas cultural tolerance and practices are related terms to the cultural environment. In this line, we again asked her that how she cope the nature and culture as her teaching profession. She narrated:

"We discuss and share our thought with other teachers and management on seasonal changes. We do also teach our students about such changes and precautions. It is good to teach our students about natural disasters too. We teach our students that we all are same besides the religion, castes or any other. We should have tolerance, talk with various language. We use "Namaste" or "Good Morning/Afternoon" as per need. Our management mostly appreciate our suggestions, plans or any programs as per practicability."

She explores that she discussed and share her thought with fellow teachers and management on seasonal changes. Later, she teaches her students about such changes and make able to take precautions after managerial decisions as per practicability. We came to know that she also taught her students on cultural tolerance against the religion, castes and language. As we probed into her practices, we understood that she used both traditional and modern greetings as "Namaste" and "Good morning/afternoon".

Finally, we queried our fourth participant, (Participant 4), on how she explained the natural and cultural environment as external factors to the school in some words. She answered that natural environment is just like weather changes, and cultural environment is different shows. In this line, we again asked her that how she cope the nature and culture as her non-teaching profession. She narrated:

"We give suggestions and aware our kids about natural changes, such as weather. We also discuss with friends, pass information and make clean and healthy kids. We support teaching staffs to conducts various cultural shows. Each class has one attendant to perform such things. I feel good that generally management and other colleagues listen our voice. However, I have no idea and plan on new programs."

Her experiences as non-teaching staff explore that she gave regular suggestion to the students about natural changes, such as weather. She also discussed with her friends, pass information and make clean and healthy environment within school, such neatness to the kids. For this purpose, each class has one attendant. She felt good that her voice is listened by her management and other teachers. She supported to conduct various cultural shows. However, she could not explain more on our queries.

IV. ESSENCES AND MEANING MAKING

The first component is people. The study of organizational behavior involves identifying need spectrum of the people, managing interpersonal relationship, understanding of individual objectives and co-relating organizational strategies accordingly. The second component, understanding of organizational structure and its modification based on the need of the hour. Manager should decide upon the nature of structure and ensure unity of command, number of levels that may be required for effective command and control. Communication, delegation of authority, well defined policies, rules, regulation, systems, procedures and processes. Introduction of latest technology is an essential part of organizational development that should be taken care of by the manager responsible for running the organization. Jobs should be allotted to the individual based on the aptitude and the processes must be compatible with the technology being used. One of the most important components is environment. While internal environment relates to various personnel policies and corresponding managerial actions, the external environment relates to cultural, social, legal, and governmental rules and regulations that should be taken care of.

In our expedition of understanding organizational behavior through the experiences of teaching and non-teaching staffs, it can be understood from the responses from the participants and with the reference from the data collection indicated that employees needed good induction and orientation from very beginning for the policies and vision of the school so as to make them perform the vision and values in the day to day living in the classroom with students and to make the working environment better with clear expectations for both parties.

(P1) stated that she was a big supporter of technology to communicate with each other as group behavior. With the support of her experiences, we understood that several students got difficulties by abuse of gadgets and got psychological issues which created stress on her individual behavior. In the next theme for external environment, she revealed her practices on various programs such as world environment day or any occasion, where she created several concepts, do planning in group, take permission from management and then implement properly. This revealed that she was active on social issues and worked efficiently with formal and informal group. And, her efforts towards natural issues proved her as social-beings. Her practices to follow both traditional and modern greetings indicated her individual believes toward the culture is indifference. Second participant (P2) also thought that the use of technology within the school was essential for twenty-first century. We came to know that her group behavior has been affected by technology. She used technologies to enhance communication with other colleagues and students through edutainment process. Her efforts to consult parents on boundaries to the technology showed that she recognized and regulated the emotional intelligence. She created the program concepts, then took permission from management and implemented everything with her co-worker point out that she loved the group-work in both formal and informal groups. Her precautions for natural disaster were the symbols of her foresightedness. Third participant (P3) also had an experience of using technologies properly. Her ability to search and learn through internet was noticeable individual behavior. She shared educational and related materials on teacher's messenger group which indicated that her group behavior was sociable and active. However, sometimes she was stressed with students' behavior who followed cartoon characters. She explored that she discussed and shared her thought with fellow teachers and management, then took permission before implementing those thoughts. She believed on cultural tolerance against the religion, castes, language or any kind of discrimination and practices both modern and traditional greetings. These indicators specified she was societal, extroverted, indifferent and wise towards the judgments. Fourth participant (P4) was novice on proper use of technology which indicates her individual behavior toward technology was passive learner. However, she agreed that technology was good for learning indicated she had agreeableness characters. We came to know that her group behavior found a bridge between school, students and parents indicates she was socially active. She suggested to the students, work in team, pass the information and many more indicates her behavior is full with trustworthiness, service orientation, teamwork and collaboration which are the major components of emotional intelligence.

After examining experiences and stories of these four participants on organizational behavior in their teaching and non-teaching roles, we came to this point of understanding that organizational behavior of an individual is directly affected by four components: people, structure, technology and external environments.

V. CONCLUSION

In our journey of understanding the organizational behavior through its four components people, structure, technology and external environment as stated by Kondalkar (2007, pp. 7-9). The study of organizational behavior relates to the study of attitude, perception, learning, values at individual level and also relates the study of pertaining to managing stress, conflicts, intergroup behavior, decision making at group level. It is the responsibility of the managers to evolve appropriate strategies to study organizational components. Mayo asserted (as stated in Kondalkar, 2007, p. 26) the following theory as human relation theory that states:

1. Individual behavior and sentiments are closely related.
2. Group influences significantly affected individual behavior.
3. Group standards established individual output.
4. Money was less a factor in determining output.
5. Group standards, group sentiments and security provided by the group were responsible for higher productivity.

The study of organizational behavior involves identifying need spectrum of the people, managing interpersonal relationship, understanding of individual objectives and co-relating organizational strategies accordingly. The second component, understanding of organizational structure and its modification based on the need of the hour. Manager should decide upon the nature of structure and ensure unity of command, number of levels that may be required for effective command and control. Communication, delegation of authority, well defined policies, rules, regulation, systems, procedures and processes. Introduction of latest technology is an essential part of organizational development that should be taken care of by the manager responsible for running the organization. Jobs should be allotted to the individual based on the aptitude and the processes must be compatible with the technology being used. One of the most important components is environment. While internal environment relates to various personnel policies and corresponding managerial actions, the external environment relates to cultural, social, legal, and governmental rules and regulations that should be taken care of.

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